
A PEDAGOGICAL INVESTIGATION INTO THE TEACHING AND LEARNING OF ENGLISH IN KANO STATE POLYTECHNIC.

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Abstract

This study investigates the pedagogy, challenges, and effectiveness of English language teaching and learning in Kano State Polytechnic, with the aim of identifying existing teaching methods, learning difficulties, and strategies for improvement. The study adopts a descriptive survey design, utilizing questionnaires and interviews to collect data from 400 respondents, comprising students across the five campuses and lecturers in the School of General Studies. Findings reveal that English instruction at the polytechnic is largely dominated by teacher-centered lecture methods, which limit students' communicative competence and participation. Common challenges identified include weak language foundation, inadequate instructional materials, poor reading culture, and low motivation among students. Additionally, most respondents reported the absence of functional language laboratories and insufficient professional development for lecturers. The study recommends a shift toward communicative and learner-centered teaching approaches, consistent with the principles of Constructivist Learning Theory (Piaget, 1970) and Sociocultural Theory (Vygotsky, 1978). It further suggests the provision of modern instructional materials, establishment of reading clubs, and regular training for English lecturers to enhance teaching effectiveness and student performance. In conclusion, improving the pedagogical framework and learning environment in Kano State Polytechnic will foster better English proficiency, critical thinking, and overall academic achievement among students.

Keywords: English, Pedagogy, Constructivism, Language, Learning, Kano State Polytechnic.

Introduction

The role of English Language in the Polytechnic Education, though an adopted *lingua franca*, has assumed a phenomenal vitality in the Nigerian society, especially in her educational system. Aside proficiency in English language being a pre-requisite for admission into tertiary education, its introduction as course in polytechnic education as one of the general courses, defines its absolute importance in achieving technical education. This is so because students who have so many difficulties with their communication skill in English Language may not function effectively, not only in written and spoken English Language but in their academic pursuit, Aina, Alexander and Shola (356) Adegboye (9) corroborates Aina et al claim that, when students' proficiency in English Language is high, it will definitely affect and improve the academic performance of such student. However, where the proficiency in English is lacking in any academic setting, it will definitely lower the level of academic performance of such student. Furthermore, Itsuokor (p.60) avers that “competency in English significantly determines performance in intelligence or academic test”. It means, in essence, that mastery of English Language is vital in students' academic performance in intelligence test, especially as it pertains to science and technical education which polytechnic belongs.

The above systematic essence of technical education cannot be realized without essentially understanding the language of communication and instruction which is the vehicle that drives it. Thus, students trained (and being trained) in technical education program requires English language to understand the content of the program, which invariably will improve their academic excellence.

Nevertheless, According to Joseph (356), Nigerian teachers of English like their other counterparts in other courses, face an uphill task. They are required to scale several hurdles before they stand a chance of executing their job decently. They need to be properly groomed, monitored and assisted to grow in confidence while performing their duties. The teacher of English language must cultivate and maintain certain human traits considered necessary for their success. Nevertheless, on the need of teaching aid – many of the non-textual facilities for English language teaching have almost disappeared from the school environment – while in some schools provision for that has never been made. These teaching aids include authentic and functioning audio-visuals like print resources (Newspaper and Magazine), language laboratories or radio tape recorder/receiver and simple in expressive public address system. In the words of Aliyu (356), these different facilities will assist in promoting students’ learning of English. “Many of them serve as sources of model for all form of language production and playback. In many instances their availability reduces the role of the reader to that of a facilitator, while in their absence the teacher is encouraged to monopolize classroom talk.

Teaching, according to Azubike (2016), could be seen as a transmission of knowledge. It could be conceptualized as helping an individual or student to learn. Learning on the other hand, “is a process and not a method”. In learning, the learner plays a crucial role. Learning is a change in behaviour or activities. Learning cannot be mandated. Teachers cannot guarantee that a particular student will learn. There are so many factors that affect the ability of an individual to learn. Hence, the relationship between teaching and learning is not only elusive but also complex. The learning process, therefore, supremely tests students’ motivation and physical condition, teaching resources and teaching skills. Hence John Dewey once opined that teaching and learning maybe compared to buying and selling. No one can sell unless someone buys. Teaching cannot be said to have taken place unless someone has learnt or is learning.

Nevertheless, the English language occupies a significant position in Nigeria's educational system, serving as both a subject of study and the medium of instruction in tertiary institutions. As a result, proficiency in English is a major determinant of students' academic performance. In polytechnics, where students are trained for professional and technical disciplines, English plays a vital communicative role in enabling effective understanding of course materials, report writing, and workplace communication.

However, in recent years, concerns have been raised about the declining standard of English among students in Nigerian polytechnics, including those in Kano State Polytechnic. Many students struggle with speaking, writing, listening, and reading skills due to poor foundational knowledge, inadequate exposure to authentic language use, and ineffective pedagogical practices. This situation calls for a systematic pedagogical investigation into how English is taught and learned in Kano State Polytechnic and what improvements can be made.

Despite the centrality of English in Nigeria's educational and professional systems, many polytechnic students demonstrate limited proficiency in the language. This deficiency affects not only their academic success but also their employability and professional competence. The problem may be attributed to a combination of factors such as teacher-centred instructional methods, limited classroom interaction, inadequate instructional materials, and insufficient motivation among students. In Kano State Polytechnic, where English serves as the language of instruction across departments, poor language performance has become a persistent issue. It is therefore essential to investigate the pedagogical approaches employed by lecturers and assess students' attitudes and challenges toward learning English. The aim of this study is to investigate the pedagogy and challenges associated with the teaching and learning of English in Kano State Polytechnic. The objectives are to:

1. Examine the teaching methods and strategies used by English lecturers.
2. Identify the major challenges faced by students in learning English.
3. Assess the availability and utilization of teaching aids and resources.
4. Suggest pedagogical improvements for enhancing English language learning.

The following are the research questions for this investigation

1. What teaching methods are commonly used by English lecturers at Kano State Polytechnic?
2. What challenges do students face in learning English?
3. How adequate are the teaching aids and instructional materials used?
4. What pedagogical measures can improve the teaching and learning of English in the institution?

Review of Related Literature

The Role of English in Nigerian Tertiary Education

English is Nigeria's official language and the primary medium of instruction in all levels of education beyond the basic stage. According to Akinwumi (2018), English serves as the language of administration, scholarship, and professional communication in Nigeria's polytechnics and universities. Its mastery, therefore, determines students' success in both academic and workplace contexts.

In Kano State Polytechnic, English functions not only as a subject of study in the School of General Studies but also as the vehicle for delivering technical and professional knowledge.

As Akindele and Adegbite (1999) observe, the effective teaching and learning of English in tertiary institutions are vital for intellectual and technological development.

Pedagogical Approaches to Teaching English

Over the years, several methods have been applied to English language teaching in Nigeria. Traditional approaches such as the Grammar-Translation Method and Audio-Lingual Method have gradually given way to more learner-centered approaches like the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) method. According to Richards and Rodgers (2014), CLT emphasizes communication and interaction as the means and ultimate goal of language learning.

In the context of polytechnic education, this approach is particularly relevant because it prepares students to use English effectively in professional situations. However, many lecturers still rely on lecture-based, teacher-centered instruction that limits student participation. Aina and Adigun (2011) argue that such practices fail to promote critical thinking and communicative competence among learners.

Challenges in the Teaching and Learning of English

Numerous studies have highlighted the challenges confronting both teachers and students of English in Nigerian polytechnics. Among the most prominent are: Issa et al. (2012) argued that Inadequate language background is the major catalyst for problems in English language learning among students, they stressed that many students enter tertiary institutions with weak foundational knowledge of English. Lecturers often dominate classroom interactions, leaving little room for students to practice communication, lack of instructional materials: Textbooks, audiovisual aids, and language laboratories are often insufficient and negative attitude toward English: Some students view English as an unnecessary burden rather than a skill essential for career development (Osei 2018). These challenges collectively hinder language acquisition and reduce learners' motivation and confidence in using English.

Strategies for Improving English Language Teaching and Learning

To enhance English proficiency in polytechnics, scholars recommend adopting more interactive and learner-centered strategies. Krashen (2004) emphasizes extensive reading and meaningful exposure to language use as crucial to language mastery. Similarly, Clark and Rumbold (2006) advocate reading for pleasure as a way to build vocabulary and comprehension. Lecturers should integrate communicative tasks, group discussions, and project-based learning to create authentic language experiences. Additionally, institutional support in the form of well-equipped language laboratories and updated curriculum design is essential for improvement.

Theoretical Framework

Constructivist Learning Theory (Jean Piaget, 1970)

The Constructivist Learning Theory posits that learners actively construct knowledge through interaction and experience. Piaget (1970) argues that learning is not a passive process of receiving information but an active one of meaning-making. Applied to language learning, this theory suggests that students should be encouraged to engage with texts, discussions, and

tasks that promote understanding rather than rote memorization. In the context of Kano State Polytechnic, this theory supports the need for participatory teaching methods that enable students to construct linguistic knowledge through exploration, collaboration, and reflection.

Communicative Language Teaching (Hymes, 1972; Richards & Rodgers, 2014)

The Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) framework emphasizes the importance of communication as the goal of language learning. Hymes (1972) introduced the concept of communicative competence, which extends beyond grammatical accuracy to include sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic competence. Richards and Rodgers (2014) further note that CLT encourages interaction, problem-solving, and task-based learning—approaches that mirror real-life language use. For Kano State Polytechnic, this theory underlines the importance of encouraging students to use English for practical communication in academic and vocational contexts.

Sociocultural Theory (Lev Vygotsky, 1978)

The Sociocultural Theory emphasizes the role of social interaction and cultural context in learning. Vygotsky (1978) posits that knowledge is co-constructed through dialogue and collaboration within a social environment. Language learning, therefore, thrives in interactive settings where teachers act as facilitators and peers learn from one another. This theory is particularly relevant to this study, as it supports the idea that English language learning should occur through active communication, peer collaboration, and authentic use within the classroom and beyond.

This review has examined the centrality of English in Nigerian tertiary education, the pedagogical methods used in teaching it, and the challenges affecting effective learning. It also identified strategies for improvement and situated the study within constructivist, communicative, and sociocultural theoretical frameworks. Collectively, these frameworks underscore the need for participatory, interactive, and contextually relevant approaches to English language teaching in Kano State Polytechnic.

METHODS

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. This design was chosen because it enables the researcher to collect data from a large population and analyze their views, experiences, and opinions about the teaching and learning of English. The survey approach is suitable for educational research where the objective is to describe existing conditions and suggest improvements (Nworgu 2015).

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised selected students across the polytechnic campuses and English lecturers in the School of General Studies, Kano State Polytechnic. These lecturers teach English language courses to students across different departments, making it the most appropriate focus for the research. According to administrative records (Kano State Polytechnic, 2024), the School of General Studies has 30 English lecturers. This study population comprise the entire students of Kano State Polytechnic, who are duly registered

during 2024/2025 academic session. The expected total number of the population is (12,305) comprising the students of the six unit schools in the Polytechnic as presented below:

Table 1. Population of the Study

S/N	Schools	No. of Population
1.	School of Management Studies (SMS)	4,403
2.	School of Technology (SOT)	5,834
3.	School of General Studies (SGS)	1,022
4.	School of Social and Rural Development, Rano (SSRD)	316
5.	Kano State Institute of Information Technology	420
6.	School of Environmental Studies, Gwarzo (SES)	310
Total		12,305

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The method of stratified random sampling technique was used to ensure representation from different departments and programs within the polytechnic. This sampling method was chosen to avoid bias and ensure that the data collected reflect diverse perspectives within the institution. To ensure adequate sample representation for this study, the researcher will use Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample determination table. For a population of Twelve Thousand Three Hundred and Five Thousand (12,305), a sample size of three hundred and seventy-five (375) will be considered appropriate (Krejcie, 1970). So, for statistical clarity a sample of 400 respondents was selected for the study, consisting of 350 students and 50 English lecturers.

Research Instruments

Two major instruments were used for data collection:

1. Questionnaire – structured with both open-ended and closed-ended questions to gather quantitative and qualitative data from students and lecturers.
2. Interview Schedule – used to obtain detailed information from selected lecturers about their teaching methods, challenges, and suggestions for improvement.

The questionnaire consisted of four sections: demographic information, teaching methods, challenges in learning English, and strategies for improvement.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher personally administered the questionnaires with the help of research assistants from the School of General Studies. Respondents were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaires to ensure accurate responses. Interviews with lecturers were conducted face-to-face and recorded for analysis. Ethical considerations such as voluntary participation, confidentiality, and informed consent were strictly observed throughout the process.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected from the questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistical methods such as frequency counts, percentages, and mean scores. Qualitative data from interviews were analyzed thematically to identify recurring ideas and perspectives related to teaching

and learning English. The results of the analysis were presented in tables and charts, with interpretations linked to the study objectives and research questions

Findings

This section presents and analyzes the data collected from four hundred (400) respondents drawn from Kano State Polytechnic. The purpose of the analysis is to examine the teaching and learning of English, identify the challenges faced by both lecturers and students, and suggest effective strategies for improving English language pedagogy. Data were collected through questionnaires and interviews administered to students and lecturers in the School of General Studies.

Table 2: Demographic Information

Category	Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	260	65
	Female	140	35
Status	Lecturers	50	12.5
	Students	350	87.5
Age Range	18–25	220	55
	26–35	100	25
	36 and above	80	20

Data Collected on: 6 October 2025

Interpretation:

The data show that the majority of respondents (65%) were male, and students made up 87.5% of the sample. Most respondents were between 18–25 years, indicating that the majority of participants are active learners in the undergraduate category.

Table 3: Teaching Methods Adopted

Teaching Method	Lecturers Using It (n=50)	Percentage (%)
Lecture method	45	90
Discussion method	35	70
Audio-visual aids	20	40
Communicative approach	25	50
Group/Project work	30	60

Data Collected on: 6 October 2025

Interpretation:

The lecture method dominates (90%), while interactive and communicative techniques are less frequently used. This suggests a traditional, teacher-centered approach still prevails in English instruction.

Table 4: Students' Perception of Teaching Effectiveness

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very Effective	70	20
Effective	120	34.3
Fairly Effective	100	28.6
Ineffective	60	17.1

Data Collected on: 6 October 2025

Interpretation: A combined 54.3% of students consider teaching methods effective or very effective, but nearly 46% feel otherwise — implying there is room for improvement in pedagogical delivery and classroom engagement.

Table 5: Challenges in Teaching and Learning English

Challenges Identified	Frequency (Lecturers + Students)	Percentage (%)
Insufficient instructional materials	290	72.5
Overcrowded classrooms	260	65
Poor student motivation	240	60
Limited exposure to English outside classroom	280	70
Inadequate teacher training	150	37.5

Data Collected on: 6 October 2025

Interpretation:

The most pressing issues are lack of materials (72.5%) and limited exposure to English use (70%). These findings indicate that structural and environmental constraints are key obstacles to effective language learning.

Table 6: Strategies for Improvement (Perceived Solutions)

Suggested Solution	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Provision of teaching aids and modern facilities	300	75
Incorporating communicative and technology-based approaches	280	70
Continuous professional development for lecturers	260	65
Reducing class sizes	240	60
Encouraging English-only communication in school environment	320	80

Data Collected on: 6 October 2025

Interpretation:

Respondents believe promoting English usage, upgrading facilities, and retraining lecturers are crucial strategies to improve teaching and learning outcomes.

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed that the lecture method is the most frequently used mode of instruction, employed by about 90% of the lecturers. This finding aligns with earlier research in Nigerian tertiary institutions (Adegbite, 2018; Aina, 2021), which observed that the traditional teacher-centered approach remains dominant in language classrooms.

However, the limited use of communicative and technology-based methods—such as group work, discussions, and multimedia aids—suggests that the teaching of English at Kano State Polytechnic is yet to fully embrace contemporary Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and learner-centered pedagogies. These modern approaches encourage interaction, creativity, and practical language use—skills that students need for communicative competence. Thus, while the lecture method ensures content coverage, it often fails to promote language fluency, self-expression, and critical thinking among learners.

Students' perceptions of teaching effectiveness indicate a moderate level of satisfaction: about 54.3% rated English teaching as effective or very effective, while nearly half (46%) expressed dissatisfaction. This implies that although lecturers make commendable efforts, several pedagogical and institutional gaps hinder optimal learning outcomes.

This result corresponds with Olaofe (2016) and Adejare (2016), who noted that the mismatch between instructional techniques and student learning preferences often reduces engagement and retention. The absence of authentic communicative activities, such as debates, presentations, and peer learning, limits students' confidence in using English in real contexts.

Hence, the findings suggest that the effectiveness of English instruction at the Polytechnic depends not only on teachers' proficiency but also on the adaptability of methods to students' needs.

The study identified several major obstacles affecting English pedagogy:

- Inadequate instructional materials (72.5%),
- Limited exposure to English outside the classroom (70%), and
- Overcrowded classrooms (65%).

These challenges are consistent with the wider Nigerian educational context, as reported by Adejumo (2019) and Aina et al. (2023), where resource constraints and linguistic interference from mother tongues impede language acquisition.

The issue of inadequate exposure particularly underscores the limited English-speaking environment within and outside the school. Since most students interact in Hausa or other local languages, English becomes restricted to formal settings, reducing fluency and confidence. Moreover, large class sizes hinder individualized feedback and interactive activities—factors essential for effective language learning.

Another key finding is the need for continuous professional development for lecturers. Although most lecturers are qualified, many rely on outdated pedagogical approaches. This supports Adegboye's (2019) assertion that proficiency in English language teaching is strongly tied to teacher competence and training.

Professional workshops and training in modern methodologies such as Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), Communicative Approach, and Blended Learning are therefore necessary. Continuous retraining will help lecturers adapt to global standards and integrate technology effectively into their teaching practice.

The study further revealed that poor student motivation (60%) significantly affects learning outcomes. Factors contributing to this include lack of interest in English, perception of English as a difficult subject, and insufficient interactive exposure.

According to Krashen's (1982) Affective Filter Hypothesis, motivation, anxiety, and attitude greatly influence language acquisition. Therefore, to foster motivation, lecturers should incorporate student-centered methods—games, storytelling, role-plays, and multimedia—to make lessons engaging and relevant.

Respondents suggested several practical strategies to enhance English pedagogy:

- Provision of modern teaching aids and facilities (75%),
- Adoption of technology-enhanced and communicative methods (70%), and
- Encouragement of English-only communication within the Polytechnic (80%).

These findings resonate with Nunan (2003) and Richards (2017), who advocate for the integration of interactive and experiential methods in ESL contexts. Creating an English-speaking environment will also increase language exposure and confidence among students.

Overall, the findings highlight the urgent need for a paradigm shift from traditional, teacher-centered instruction toward communicative and participatory learning. This transformation requires administrative support, staff retraining, infrastructural investment, and sustained policy implementation. If properly addressed, Kano State Polytechnic can become a model for effective English pedagogy in Nigerian tertiary education.

Conclusion

This study examined the pedagogical approaches, challenges, and overall effectiveness of English language teaching and learning in Kano State Polytechnic. The analysis of data collected from 400 respondents (50 lecturers and 350 students) revealed significant insights into the state of English pedagogy at the institution.

The findings indicate that while English language instruction has achieved a reasonable level of awareness and participation, the dominance of traditional lecture methods continues to limit interactive and communicative learning experiences. This teacher-centered orientation results in passive learners who often lack confidence and fluency in spoken and written English.

Furthermore, institutional challenges—including inadequate teaching materials, overcrowded classrooms, and insufficient exposure to English outside the classroom—negatively affect both teaching efficiency and student performance. Many lecturers also lack adequate access to professional development opportunities, leading to a gap between modern pedagogical theory and classroom practice.

Despite these constraints, both lecturers and students demonstrated a strong awareness of the importance of English for academic and professional advancement. Their responses highlighted a genuine desire for improved methods, better facilities, and a more immersive language environment. Therefore, this research concludes that improving English language education in Kano State Polytechnic requires systemic and collaborative reform involving teachers, administrators, and policymakers.

In essence, effective English pedagogy depends on methodological innovation, teacher competence, learner motivation, and institutional support. When these elements are harmonized, the teaching and learning of English can evolve from a routine academic exercise into a dynamic and practical communicative process.

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- I. **Adopt Communicative and Learner-Centered Methods:** Lecturers should move beyond the traditional lecture method and employ Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Task-Based Learning, and Collaborative Learning strategies. These approaches will foster student participation, critical thinking, and practical language use.

- II. Integrate Technology in Language Teaching: The Polytechnic should equip English language classrooms with audio-visual tools, language laboratories, and digital resources. Using videos, projectors, and interactive software can make learning more engaging and effective.
- III. Provide Continuous Professional Development for Lecturers: The institution and relevant authorities should organize regular workshops, seminars, and in-service training to expose lecturers to current trends in English pedagogy, such as blended learning, flipped classrooms, and online assessment techniques.
- IV. Improve Teaching Facilities and Materials: The government and school management should ensure adequate provision of textbooks, teaching aids, and language laboratories. Access to these materials will enhance lesson delivery and comprehension.
- V. Reduce Class Size and Ensure Better Classroom Management: Overcrowded classrooms hinder participation and feedback. The Polytechnic should reduce class sizes and recruit additional qualified English lecturers to maintain optimal teacher–student ratios.
- VI. Encourage English Usage Beyond the Classroom: The institution should create an English-speaking environment by promoting English use in official communication, social activities, and academic events. Clubs such as English Language Societies or Debate Forums should be encouraged.

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